

Studies in Formation and Properties of Carbon-Oxygen Surface Complexes : Part IV. Chemisorption Kinetics of Oxygen on Charcoal and Nature of the Complexes Formed

Balwant Rai Puri, D. D. Singh and K. C. Sehgal

Chemisorption kinetics of oxygen on an ash-free outgassed sugar charcoal, before and after 38% burn-off in oxygen at 650°, 200°, 300° and 350° under oxygen pressure of one atmosphere have been studied. The data have been found to follow the Elovich equation, and reveal that chemisorption occurs in two stages involving two different types of sites. The more active sites are involved in the formation of the non-acidic 'CO₂-complex' while the less active sites are involved in the formation of the 'CO-complex'. The more energetic sites at which the 'CO₂-complex' is formed have been identified as the 'unsaturated' sites which are also involved in the fixation of bromine from aqueous solution. About half of the oxygen chemisorbed as the 'CO-complex' appears to be present as the quinonic oxygen.

The kinetics of chemisorption of oxygen on a variety of carbons under different conditions of temperature and pressure have been engaging increasing attention in recent years¹⁻⁵. The data have been found to be generally in accordance with the Elovich equation⁵. Recently, Walker and Co-workers^{6,7} studied the kinetics of chemisorption of oxygen on Graphon, before as well as after pre-oxidation to 16.6% burn-off at 625°, at 25° under oxygen pressure ranging from 0.7 millitorr to 760 torr, as well as in the temperature range -78° to 160° at a constant oxygen pressure of 100 millitorr. The plots of the amount of oxygen chemisorbed versus log of time showed five linear regions indicating the presence of five different types of adsorption sites. The chemisorbed oxygen was found to come off as carbon monoxide on evacuating the treated samples at 900°. In their technique, however, even if some of oxygen was desorbed as carbon dioxide at lower temperature it would have been reduced to carbon monoxide by the carbon itself at the prevailing temperature at 900°.

In view of the observations of Puri *et al.*⁸ that the chemisorbed oxygen usually comes off as carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide and that the complex capable of evolving carbon dioxide (the CO₂-complex) is more easily formed and also more easily eliminated, it was thought of interest to study chemisorption kinetics of oxygen on a certain charcoal of large surface area at different temperatures under oxygen pressure of one atmosphere, and to examine the nature of the oxygen complexes formed as well as the nature of the adsorption sites involved in the process.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar charcoal outgassed at 1100° in vacuum of the order of 10^{-4} mm. of mercury was used in these investigations. The sample was essentially free of oxygen but contained 1.08% hydrogen. The nitrogen B.E.T. area was $442 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. The active surface area, as calculated from the amount of oxygen chemisorbed at 350° under oxygen pressure of one atmosphere assuming one oxygen atom to be fixed per active carbon atom occupying an area of 8.3 \AA^2 ,⁹ was calculated to be 16.9% of the nitrogen area.

The charcoal was also activated in oxygen at 650° to 38% burn-off. This increased the nitrogen area to $496 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. and the active surface area to about 20% of the total area.

The kinetics of chemisorption were studied at 200, 300 and 350° in a volumetric apparatus consisting essentially of reaction vessel connected to one limb of a mercury manometer; the manometer also served the purpose of a gas burette. The manometer was connected to a mercury reservoir which could be raised or lowered in order to adjust the level of mercury in the gas burette. The reaction vessel and the gas burette could be connected either to vacuum or to the pure oxygen supply, as the case may be. The reaction vessel was surrounded by a resistance tube furnace the temperature of which could be adjusted at any desired level within $\pm 2^{\circ}$.

Charcoal ($\sim 1 \text{ g}$., oven dried) was taken in the reaction vessel and outgassed at the reaction temperature for a period of about 20 hrs. A known volume of oxygen was introduced into the gas burette and the reading recorded after adjusting the mercury reservoir so as to keep the gas inside at atmospheric pressure. The burette was then connected to the reaction vessel by opening the intervening tap. The burette readings were taken after every 2–5 minutes in the initial stages of the reaction; the time interval was, however, increased to 20–50 mins after the reaction had slowed down. The volume of oxygen chemisorbed after any particular interval of time was calculated from the change in burette reading which was corrected for the known volume of the dead space. After completion of the reaction, which took about 8–9 hrs, the charcoal was allowed to cool and stored in well-corked bottles flushed with nitrogen.

The products after chemisorption were outgassed at gradually increasing temperatures upto 1200° . The gas (a mixture of carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide) evolved at any given temperature was removed from the system before the temperature of the furnace was allowed to rise by next 50° . The gases evolved were analysed for carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide by the procedure described earlier⁸.

Barium hydroxide values, as a measure of surface acidity¹⁰, and bromine adsorption value as a measure of surface unsaturation¹⁰, were determined as before.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amounts of oxygen chemisorbed at 200, 300 and 350° on the 1100° -outgassed sugar charcoal before and after pre-activation to 38 percent burn-off in oxygen, have been

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plotted against time in Fig. 1 and 2, respectively. It is seen that chemisorption proceeds fairly rapidly in the beginning but slows down with time as more and more surface sites get covered up with oxygen.

Fig. 1. Amounts of oxygen chemisorbed on 1100°-outgassed sugar charcoal on treatment in oxygen at different temperatures for different intervals of time before burn-off.

Fig. 2. Amounts of oxygen chemisorbed on 1100°-outgassed sugar charcoal on treatment in oxygen at different temperatures for different intervals of time after 68 percent burn-off.

The magnitude of the chemisorption, during any given time interval or at the end of the reaction (after 500 mins), is seen to increase with the temperature of the reaction. Taking total active surface area as equal to that obtained from the amount of oxygen chemisorbed at 350° in the manner discussed above, it can be shown that the fractions of the active surface covered at 200 and 300° amount to about 54% and 82% respectively, before as well as after the pre-activation of the charcoal. The increase in the amount of chemisorption in the case of activated charcoal (cf. Fig. 1 and 2), therefore, appears to be due to the creation of new active surface area during the burn-off at 650°.

According to the Elovich equation, which though empirical and not without limitations^{11,12} has found wide applications in chemisorption kinetics⁵⁻⁷.

$$dq/dt = ae^{-\alpha q}$$

Fig. 3. q - $\log t$ plots for chemisorption of oxygen on 1100°-outgassed sugar charcoal at different temperatures before burn-off.

where q is the amount of gas chemisorbed and ' a ' and ' α ' are constants. In the integrated form the equation may be put as

$$q = 2.3/\alpha \log (\alpha at + 1)$$

A plot of q versus $\log t$, therefore, should be a straight line.

Fig. 4. q - $\log t$ plots for chemisorption of oxygen on 1100°-outgassed sugar charcoal at different temperatures after 38 percent burn-off.

11. I. S. Melintock, *Journal of Catalysis*, 1970, **16**, 126.

12. S. Mizushima, *Proc. Fifth Carbon Conf.*, Pergamon Press, 1963, **2**, 439.

The q -log t plots of our data are shown in Fig. 3 and 4. It is seen that the points fit on two straight lines of different slopes indicating discontinuous linear regions. This means that at the experimental temperature and under oxygen pressure of one atmosphere, two different types of sites are involved, probably, in the process. In this respect our results seem to be in harmony with those of Walker, Bansal and Vastola on chemisorption of oxygen on Graphon at room temperature and oxygen pressure approaching one atmosphere⁶ and also at low oxygen pressure but at increasing temperatures⁷.

TABLE I

Parameters of the Elovich equation for chemisorption of oxygen on 1100°-outgassed sugar charcoal at different temperatures before and after 38 percent burn-off

Temperature of treatment °C	Before burn-off				After 38 percent burn-off			
	First kinetic stage		Second kinetic stage		First kinetic stage		Second kinetic stage	
	α (mg/g) ⁻¹	a (mg/g per min.)						
200	0.60	1.99	0.29	0.03	0.57	9.82	0.21	0.05
300	0.58	13.10	0.29	0.17	0.56	69.21	0.22	0.28
350	0.57	35.12	0.31	0.67	0.57	151.10	0.22	0.87

An insight into the nature of the two types of sites involved in the chemisorption process can be gained from the values of ' α ' and ' a ' (Table I) calculated from the Elovich equation using the method of Allardice⁵. The values of ' α ' are seen to be independent of temperature, as expected. The values of ' a ', the initial rate constants, are seen to be temperature dependent, the values rising appreciably with rise in temperature. At a given temperature and for a given kinetic stage, the value is higher for the pre-activated sample. At a given temperature, the value is much higher for the first kinetic stage than for the second. This shows that the type-2 sites (sites involved in the chemisorption during the second kinetic stage) are less active than the type-1 sites. This conclusion is also borne out by the values of activation energies for chemisorption on two types of sites, obtained from the Arrhenius plots. The values for type-1 and type-2 sites come out to be 10.7 and 12.8 Kcal, respectively for the 1100°-outgassed charcoal, and 9.9 and 11.1 Kcal. for the pre-activated charcoal. These values are of the same order as reported by previous workers^{5,6}.

Nature of the oxygen complexes formed : Since the two types of sites are energetically different, the complexes formed at these might be of different nature. In order to obtain information about this aspect of the problem, the products obtained after completion of the reaction¹ at each temperature and in some cases, after completion of the first kinetic stage and before the commencement of the second, were examined for the disposition of the chemisorbed oxygen and for a few other characteristic properties such as base adsorption capacity, bromine adsorption value, hydrogen uptake in the sodium borohydride reaction etc.

The analysis of the gases evolved on evacuating the two charcoals after completion of the reaction at each temperature (Table II) shows that (i) the values of oxygen chemisorbed, as obtained from the amount of oxygen consumed during the experiment, agree very well with those obtained as carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide in the evacuation experiments, (ii) the pattern of disposition of the chemisorbed oxygen does not undergo any change after pre-activation of the charcoal, (iii) the ratio of oxygen evolved as carbon dioxide to that evolved as carbon monoxide is greater than one at each temperature but decreases significantly with increase of temperature of chemisorption. These observations indicate that although the complexes capable of evolving carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide are formed at all temperatures between 200 to 350°, those capable of evolving carbon dioxide are formed more readily at lower temperatures and those capable of evolving carbon monoxide are formed more readily at higher temperatures.

TABLE II

Chemisorption of oxygen on 1100°-outgassed sugar charcoal at different temperatures before and after 38% burn-off, after completion of the reaction and after the end of the first kinetic stage

Temperature of treatment °C	Amount of oxygen chemisorbed (mg/g.) after completion of the reaction			Amount of oxygen chemisorbed (mg/g.) after the end of the first kinetic stage				
	Obtained directly from chemisorption measurements	Obtained by evacuation at 1200°C as		Obtained directly from chemisorption measurements	Obtained by evacuation at 1200°C as			
		CO ₂	CO	Total		CO ₂	CO	Total
Before burn-off								
200	12.5	8.2	3.9	12.1	7.0	6.9	0.2	7.1
300	20.2	12.0	8.6	20.6	8.8	8.7	0.3	9.0
350	24.0	13.2	10.9	24.1	—	—	—	—
After 38 percent burn-off								
200	17.9	10.9	6.9	17.8	9.6	9.5	0.3	9.8
300	25.4	14.6	10.6	25.2	10.8	10.6	0.4	11.0
350	32.0	16.8	15.4	32.2	—	—	—	—

The results of outgassing four samples, in which chemisorption was interrupted before the commencement of the second kinetic stage (given in Table II), reveal that type-1 sites (the more active sites) are involved largely in the formation of the complex capable of evolving carbon dioxide; types-2 sites, therefore, must be the ones involved in the formation of the complex capable of evolving carbon monoxide.

The complexes capable of evolving carbon dioxide are generally considered to be acidic in nature¹³ but the possibility of the formation of a non-acidic complex capable of evolving carbon dioxide has also been indicated recently by Puri *et al.*⁸. The base adsorption capacities of the products (included in Table III) do not suggest the development

TABLE III

Break-up of chemisorbed oxygen evolved on evacuating the products at 1200° along with their base adsorption capacity and surface unsaturation

Temperature of treatment °C	Oxygen evolved as CO ₂ on evacuating the product milli g atoms/100g.	Base adsorption capacity milli eq./100 g.	Amount of non-acidic CO ₂ -complex formed (milli eq./100 g.) or amount of oxygen fixed at unsaturated sites milli g. atoms/100 g.		Surface unsaturation milli g. atoms of bromine/100 g.		Oxygen evolved as CO on evacuating the product mg/g.	Quinonic oxygen mg/g.
			Before burn-off	After 38 percent burn-off	Before treatment	After treatment		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
200	51	nil	51	391	337	3.9	2.0	
300	75	nil	75	391	315	8.6	4.4	
350	83	nil	83	391	307	10.9	5.5	
After 38 percent burn-off								
200	68	nil	68	405	335	6.9	3.5	
300	91	nil	91	405	311	10.6	5.4	
350	105	nil	105	405	298	15.4	7.6	

of any acidity. The pH value of the products was found to remain close to 7.4. This indicates the formation of the non-acidic CO₂-complex. It is highly probable that this non-acidic complex is formed through addition of oxygen at the unsaturated sites. This view receives support from an almost equivalent decrease in surface unsaturation as estimated by the bromine adsorption value¹⁰ (cf. Table III, col. 5 and 6), in all the samples after chemisorption of oxygen; the bromine value being a measure of the surface unsaturation¹⁰.

Regarding the nature of the CO-complex, the possibilities are for the formation of quinonic, ethereal or some other yet unidentified groups¹⁴. The phenolic type CO-complex does not appear to be formed since there is no development of acidity in charcoals after chemisorption. The amounts of quinonic oxygen (Table III, col. 8) as obtained from the uptake of hydrogen in sodium borohydride reaction¹⁵, are seen to constitute only about half of the oxygen evolved as carbon monoxide, the rest of the oxygen fixed at the type-2 sites appears to be present in some other form.

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Department of Chemistry,
Panjab University,
Chandigarh.

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